

SUPOLAR and SUPOFILT: SU programs for polarization analysis and filtering of three-component data

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This is a brief description of the mathematical basis of the programs `supolar` and `supofilt` and the set of values of the calculated time sequences. Both programs have been developed as part of my diploma thesis in geophysics (Maercklin, 1999) and are now included in *Seismic Unix* Release 35 and higher (Cohen and Stockwell, 2001). The filter `supofilt` remained unchanged, and the updated version of `supolar` described here is still compatible with the initial version from my thesis (same defaults etc.). After Section 1 on horizontal rotation of three-component data, Section 2 introduces the polarization attributes that can be computed with `supolar`. Section 3 describes the polarization filter implemented in `supofilt`, and Section 4 provides usage information for the two programs. Additional programs are mentioned in the final Section 5.

1 Horizontal rotation

Three-component data can be rotated from one coordinate system to another before or after polarization analysis and filtering. Often, the data shall be analyzed in a coordinate system consisting of the vertical component Z , a radial component R , and a transverse component T (vertical, inline, crossline). The mathematical operation

$$\begin{pmatrix} Z \\ R \\ T \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\phi) & \sin(\phi) \\ 0 & -\sin(\phi) & \cos(\phi) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Z \\ Y \\ X \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

rotates the data horizontally from the initial system (Z, Y, X) , e.g. vertical, North, East, into the new system (Z, R, T) . The acquisition geometry determines the rotation angle

$$\phi = \arctan\left(\frac{y_g - y_s}{x_g - x_s}\right) \quad (2)$$

with the source coordinates (x_s, y_s) and the receiver coordinates (x_g, y_g) .

If the receiver orientation is initially unknown, e.g. for three-component OBS data, the rotation angle ϕ may be determined by a polarization analysis of the direct phase (see Section 2.1). *Seismic Unix* Release 35 or higher includes my program `suhrot` for horizontal rotation of three-component data by any angle ϕ .

2 Polarization analysis

The superposition of three monofrequent oscillations that are orthogonal to each other leads to the formation of a polarization ellipsoid. Its orientation in space depends on phase differences between the oscillations. Seismic signals are not monofrequent but characterized by a frequency band. Therefore, during the transit of a seismic wave, subsurface particles follow a complex trajectory, the hodograph, instead of a simple ellipsoid. For a time window of N samples, this hodograph can be fit to an ellipsoid in a least-squares sense by means of a covariance analysis (Cliet and Dubesset, 1988).

¹Document created in April 2001 and slightly updated in January 2007; <http://purl.org/net/nils/man/supolar>.

The program `supolar` performs a polarization analysis of three-component data based on the covariance matrix $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}}$ to fit the data to the polarization ellipsoid. The three eigenvectors \mathbf{V}_1 , \mathbf{V}_2 , and \mathbf{V}_3 of

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}} = \begin{pmatrix} \text{Var}(X) & \text{Cov}(X, Y) & \text{Cov}(X, Z) \\ \text{Cov}(Y, X) & \text{Var}(Y) & \text{Cov}(Y, Z) \\ \text{Cov}(Z, X) & \text{Cov}(Z, Y) & \text{Var}(Z) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cov}(X, Y) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=-L}^L [X_k(t) - \mu_x][Y_k(t) - \mu_y] \\ \text{Var}(X) &= \text{Cov}(X, X) \end{aligned}$$

define the principal axes of the ellipsoid. Here, $L = (N - 1)/2$ indicates the half window length and μ the mean value of each time sequence within the analyzed window. The eigenvectors \mathbf{V}_i and the associated eigenvalues λ_i satisfy the equation

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}}\mathbf{V}_i = \lambda_i \mathbf{V}_i, \quad (4)$$

which is solved by Jacobi iteration (e.g. Press *et al.*, 1996). The eigenvalues are commonly sorted in decreasing order. The eigenvector \mathbf{V}_1 associated with the largest eigenvalue λ_1 points into the direction of the principal axis of the polarization ellipsoid (Kanasewich, 1981, 1990). This is the propagation direction of a *P*-wave and is perpendicular to it for *S*-waves.

The time window (N samples) should include about one or two mean signal periods. Smaller time windows lead to instabilities and larger ones possibly average over several phases and thus limit the resolution of the analysis. Furthermore, a possible data preprocessing has to be applied in the same manner for all three components, and bandpass filter operators must be zero-phase to avoid artefacts.

Several polarization attributes can be calculated from the eigenvalues and associated eigenvectors. These attributes describe the main polarization direction (principal direction of oscillation), the degree of linear polarization, and the distribution of energy within the selected time window (e.g. Kanasewich, 1981, 1990; Jurkevics, 1988; Maercklin, 1999). The attributes computed by `supolar` are defined in the following sections.

2.1 Direction of polarization

The direction of polarization can be described by a horizontal azimuth angle Φ and the deviation from the vertical direction or the incidence angle Θ :

$$\Theta = \arctan \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{z} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{or } \Theta = \arccos(|z|) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } \Phi = \arctan \left(\frac{y}{x} \right) \quad (7)$$

Here, x and y denote the two horizontal components of \mathbf{V}_1 and z the vertical component (direction cosines). The orientation of the polarization ellipsoid in space is ambiguous and generally has a 180° -uncertainty. The range of values `supolar` computes by default for Φ and Θ defined in Equation 5 and Equation 7 is $\pm\pi/2$ rad ($\pm 90^\circ$, if option `angle=deg` is set). The angle Θ in Equation 6 has values between 0 and 2π ($0-90^\circ$). Refer to the self-documentation of `supolar` (page 6) for details.

2.2 Shape parameters and quality of polarization

The shape parameters describe the shape of the signal and its degree of linear or planar polarization, often termed quality of polarization.

2.2.1 Ellipticities

The ratio of the semiminor to the semimajor axis of the polarization ellipsoid is called ellipticity. It describes the degree of opening of the ellipse. There are three ellipticities defined:

$$\text{principal ellipticity} \quad e_{21} = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1}} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{subprincipal ellipticity} \quad e_{31} = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_1}} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{transverse ellipticity} \quad e_{32} = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_2}} \quad (10)$$

For linear polarized events $e_{ik} = 0$, elliptical polarization yields $0 < e_{ik} < 1$, and with $e_{ik} = 1$ there is no privileged direction of polarization.

2.2.2 Rectilinearity

The rectilinearity RL is a measure of the degree of linear polarization of an event. Three different variants of RL can be computed with `supolar`. The most simple definition of RL is given by Kanasewich (1981, 1990) as

$$RL = 1 - \left(\frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} \right)^Q \quad (11)$$

With this definition the range of values is between $RL = 0$ for elliptical polarization and $RL = 1$ for exactly linear polarization. The contrast factor Q determines the sensitivity for certain degrees of polarization. Usually its value is set to $Q \leq 1$.

The rectilinearity definition of Jurkevics (1988) evaluates all three eigenvalues:

$$RL = 1 - \left(\frac{\lambda_2 + \lambda_3}{2\lambda_1} \right)^Q \quad (12)$$

where a value of $RL = 0$ indicates an undetermined direction of polarization and $RL = 1$ again perfect linear polarization. Both, the definition given by Equation 11 and Equation 12 may be used in a polarization filter (Section 3).

Meyer (1988, 1989) uses a definition that is slightly different from that of Jurkevics (1988). He defines

$$RL = 1 - \left(\frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} + \frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_1} \right)^Q \quad (13)$$

Setting $Q = 1$ yields $RL = 1$ for a straight line ($\lambda_1 \neq 0, \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = 0$), $RL = 0$ for a circle ($\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 \neq 0, \lambda_3 = 0$), and $RL = -1$ for a sphere ($\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3$). This definition of RL is not suitable for a polarization filter as described in Section 3.

2.2.3 Global polarization parameter

The meaning of the global polarization parameter τ is similar to that of the rectilinearity defined by Equation 12. It is first mentioned by Samson (1973) and defined as

$$\tau^2 = \frac{\left(1 - \frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1}\right)^2 + \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} - \frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_1}\right)^2}{2 \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} + \frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_1}\right)^2} \quad (14)$$

A straight line gives $\tau = 1$, a circle $\tau = 0.5$ and a sphere $\tau = 0$ ($\tau \in [0, 1]$).

2.2.4 Linearity coefficient

Also the linearity coefficient l_1 leads to results comparable to those of the rectilinearity or the global polarization parameter Meyer (1988, 1989). It is computed using the ellipticities defined in Section 2.2.1:

$$l_1 = 1 - \frac{3(e_{21} + e_{31})}{2(1 + e_{21} + e_{31})} \quad (15)$$

Examples from its range of values $l_1 \in [0, 1]$ are $l_1 = 1$ for exactly linear polarization, $l_1 = 0.25$ for a flat circle and $l_1 = 0$, if no privileged direction of polarization exists.

2.2.5 Flatness coefficient and planarity

The flatness or oblateness coefficient f_1 determines the degree of plane polarization (Benhama *et al.*, 1988). The particle trajectory within this plane is not further specified. Like most other shape parameters, f_1 has values between 0 and 1. In case of planar polarization the flatness coefficient is $f_1 = 1$ and in case of an undetermined polarization $f_1 = 0$.

$$f_1 = \frac{\sqrt{\lambda_1} + \sqrt{\lambda_2} - 2\sqrt{\lambda_3}}{\sqrt{\lambda_1} + \sqrt{\lambda_2} + \sqrt{\lambda_3}} = 1 - \frac{3e_{31}}{1 + e_{21} + e_{31}} \quad (16)$$

Jurkevics (1988) describes the degree of planarity by the planarity measure

$$PL = 1 - \frac{2\lambda_3}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2} \quad , \quad (17)$$

which has the same set of values as the flatness coefficient f_1 , i.e. $PL \in [0, 1]$.

2.3 Amplitude parameters

Three amplitude parameters describe the energy distribution of the wave field within the analysis time window Meyer (1988).

The instantaneous resultant

$$R_i = \sqrt{x^2(t_i) + y^2(t_i) + z^2(t_i)} \quad (18)$$

is the magnitude of the displacement vector at time t_i . The square of it, R_i^2 , is proportional to the energy of the wave field at time t_i .

The eigenresultant

$$R_e = \sqrt{\lambda_1} \quad (19)$$

determines the energy of the wave field in the direction of polarization, with λ_1 denoting the largest eigenvalue of the covariance matrix $\underline{\mathbf{M}}$.

The quadratic resultant

$$R_q = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (x_k^2 + y_k^2 + z_k^2) \quad (20)$$

is a measure for the average energy within the entire time window of N in samples. Only the eigenresultant (Equation 19) is a polarization attribute.

3 Polarization filter

One parameter for the rectilinearity or polarization quality and the orientation of the polarization ellipsoid in space can be used to construct a simple polarization filter Kanasewich (1981, 1990). This can be done with the program `supofilt`. The polarization parameters have to be computed with `supolar` first. The following equation describe the weighted directivity filter implemented in `supofilt`.

First define a weighting function of the form

$$\hat{R}(t_i) = [F(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3)]^J \quad (21)$$

at each time sample t_i , where $F(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3)$ is a measure for the quality of polarization. This can be for example the rectilinearity RL (Equations 11 and 12) or the global polarization parameter τ (Equation 14).

As mentioned above, the components of the eigenvector \mathbf{V}_1 corresponding to the largest eigenvalue λ_1 determine the direction of polarization (direction cosines; Section 2.1). With $|\mathbf{V}_1| = 1$ and $\mathbf{V}_1 = (v_{1,1}, v_{1,2}, v_{1,3})$ it is possible to define three directivity functions.

$$D_j(t_i) = (|v_{i,j}|)^K \quad (22)$$

for each time sample, where $j = x, y, z$.

A multiplication of $\hat{R}(t_i)$ and $D_j(t_i)$ with the original data yields the filter result. However, sometimes it is advantageous to smooth the filter operators over a time window of length M to minimize contributions of anomalous spikes. The smoothing operators are given by

$$\tilde{R} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=-L}^L \hat{R}(t_i + k) \quad (23)$$

$$\tilde{D}_j = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=-L}^L D_j(t_i + k) \quad , \quad (24)$$

where $L = (M - 1)/2$ denotes the half window length. Now the filtered data can be written as

$$X_f(t) = X(t)\tilde{R}(t)\tilde{D}_x(t) \quad (25)$$

$$Y_f(t) = Y(t)\tilde{R}(t)\tilde{D}_y(t) \quad (26)$$

$$Z_f(t) = Z(t)\tilde{R}(t)\tilde{D}_z(t) \quad (27)$$

In most cases the data will be filtered with a zero-phase bandpass to limit the spectral content of the data. Kanasewich (1981, 1990) suggests half of the correlation window length for the smoothing operator length, and for the exponents he suggests $J = 1$ and $K = 2$. Set $J = 0$ or $K = 0$, if only a direction filter or a linearity filter shall be applied.

4 Program manual

This section covers installation and usage of `supolar` and `supofilt`, including some shell script examples. The `demos` directory of *Seismic Unix (SU)* contains additional demonstration shell scripts. A basic knowledge of *SU* and Unix shell scripts is assumed here.

4.1 Installation

The programs `supolar` and `supofilt` are already part of *SU* Release 35 or higher (Cohen and Stockwell, 2001), i.e. a separate installation is not required. To install *SU* on your computer, follow the guidelines provided in the README files of the package and in the *SU* manual (e.g. Stockwell and Cohen, 2002). However, if you for example modified one of the programs and want to recompile it, you may use `gcc` with these command line options:

```
gcc -I${CWPROOT}/include supolar.c -L${CWPROOT}/lib -lsu -lpar -lcwp -lm -osupolar
```

Replace `supolar` by `supofilt` to compile that program, add `-O` to optimize the machine code, or add `-g` to include debug information. The environment variable `$CWPROOT` points to the directory of your *SU* installation.

4.2 Self documentations

Both, `supolar` and `supofilt`, read and write data in the SEG-Y format for *SU*, i.e. SEG-Y traces only, often referred to as *SU* format (Stockwell and Cohen, 2002). Required trace header entries are `ns`, the number of samples per trace, and the time sampling interval `dt`. As required by most *SU* programs, trace length and sampling must be the same for all traces in the input stream. If `dt` is not set in the trace header or in the command line, `supolar` assumes 0.004 s. On output none of the header entries is modified.

Three adjacent traces of the input data are interpreted as one three-component dataset. Each polarization parameter computed by `supolar` is written into its own *SU* file, usually one trace per three-component dataset. In general the order of the components does not matter, only the angle parameters Θ and Φ expect the vertical component as the first trace of one three-component set. Typical trace orders are vertical, inline, crossline, or vertical, North, East. Note that neither `supolar` nor `supofilt` check for the correct trace order.

The moving analysis time window can have four different shapes: a simple boxcar (default), or a tapered Hanning, Bartlett, or Welsh window (see e.g. Sheriff, 1991).

Like all other *SU* programs, `supolar` and `supofilt` have a self documentation explaining the usage and all required and optional command line parameters. Enter e.g. `supolar` to display the self-doc of this program (`sudoc supolar` for some more information).

4.2.1 Self-doc of supolar

```
SUPOLAR - POLarization analysis of three-component data
```

```
supolar <stdin [optional parameters]
```

```
Required parameters:
```

```
  none
```

```
Optional parameters:
```

```
dt=(from header)  time sampling intervall in seconds
wl=0.1             correlation window length in seconds
win=boxcar         correlation window shape, choose "boxcar",
                  "hanning", "bartlett", or "welsh"
file=polar         base of output file name(s)
rl=1               1 = rectilinearity evaluating 2 eigenvalues,
                  2, 3 = rectilinearity evaluating 3 eigenvalues
rlq=1.0           contrast parameter for rectilinearity
dir=1              1 = 3 components of direction of polarization
```

```

                                (the only three-component output file)
tau=0                          1 = global polarization parameter
ellip=0                         1 = principal, subprincipal, and transverse
                                ellipticities e21, e31, and e32
pln=0                           1 = planarity measure
f1=0                             1 = flatness or oblateness coefficient
l1=0                             1 = linearity coefficient
amp=0                           1 = amplitude parameters: instantaneous,
                                quadratic, and eigenresultant ir, qr, and er
theta=0                         1, 2, 3 = incidence angle of principal axis
phi=0                           1, 2, 3 = horizontal azimuth of principal axis
angle=rad                       unit of angles theta and phi, choose "rad",
                                "deg", or "gon"
all=0                           1, 2, 3 = set all output flags to that value
verbose=0                       1 = echo additional information

```

Notes:

Three adjacent traces are considered as one three-component dataset.

Correct calculation of angles theta and phi requires the first of these traces to be the vertical component, followed by the two horizontal components (e.g. Z, N, E, or Z, inline, crossline). Significant signal energy on Z is necessary to resolve the 180 deg ambiguity of phi (options phi=2,3 only).

Each calculated polarization attribute is written into its own SU file. These files get the same base name (set with "file=") and the parameter flag as an extension (e.g. polar.rl).

In case of a tapered correlation window, the window length wl may have to be increased compared to the boxcar case, because of their smaller effective widths (Bartlett, Hanning: 1/2, Welsh: 1/3).

Range of values:

parameter	option	interval	
rl	1, 2	0.0 ... 1.0	(1.0: linear polarization)
rl	3	-1.0 ... 1.0	
tau, l1	1	0.0 ... 1.0	(1.0: linear polarization)
pln, f1	1	0.0 ... 1.0	(1.0: planar polarization)
e21, e31, e32	1	0.0 ... 1.0	(0.0: linear polarization)
theta	1	-pi/2... pi/2	rad
theta	2, 3	0.0 ... pi/2	rad
phi	1	-pi/2... pi/2	rad
phi	2	-pi ... pi	rad (see notes above)
phi	3	0.0 ... 2 pi	rad (see notes above)

4.2.2 Self-doc of supofilt

SUPOFILT - Polarization FILTER for three-component data

supofilt <stdin >stdout [optional parameters]

Required parameters:

```

dfile=polar.dir  file containing the 3 components of the
                  direction of polarization
wfile=polar.rl   file name of weighting polarization parameter

```

Optional parameters:

```
dt=(from header)  time sampling intervall in seconds
smooth=1          1 = smooth filter operators, 0 do not
sl=0.05           smoothing window length in seconds
wpow=1.0          raise weighting function to power wpow
dpow=1.0          raise directivity functions to power dpow
verbose=0         1 = echo additional information
```

Notes:

Three adjacent traces are considered as one three-component dataset.

This program SUPOFILT is an extension to the polarization analysis program supolar. The files wfile and dfile are SU files as written by SUPOLAR.

4.3 Shell script examples

When working with three-component data, it is convenient to set the three-component station number and a component identification number to appropriate trace header words. The station number may be stored in `tracf`, and `trid` may be used as component identifier. Since *SU* Release 39.8 (summer 2006), the `trid` values 12, 13, and 14 are recommended for the vertical, crossline, and inline component, respectively (43, 44, 45 in previous releases). For information on the `trid` header, type `sukeyword trid`. However, all the current *SU* programs for three-component processing do not check and do not modify these trace header values.

4.3.1 Data preparation

The three files `comp1.su`, `comp2.su`, and `comp3.su` may each contain one component of the data, i.e. the vertical component and two horizontal components, respectively. The header `trid` shall be set to 12, 13, and 14 to identify the individual components, and `tracf` shall be set as a three-component station code, assuming that the traces in the files `comp?.su` are in the same order. The following commands, preferably executed within a shell script, prepare a three-component data file `data3c.su` for processing with `supolar`, `supofilt`, or other three-component *SU* tools:

```
sushw <comp1.su key=trid,tracf a=12,1 b=0,1 >data3c.temp
sushw <comp2.su key=trid,tracf a=13,1 b=0,1 >>data3c.temp
sushw <comp3.su key=trid,tracf a=14,1 b=0,1 >>data3c.temp

susort <data3c.temp >data3c.su tracf trid
rm data3c.temp
```

The file `data3c.su` is now sorted by increasing station number, with the same value of `tracf` for all traces of one three-component recording. Individual components can be identified by the value of `trid`. A zero-phase bandpass filter may be applied with `subfilt` to `data3c.su`, and an optional horizontal rotation (Section 1) is possible with `suhrot`.

4.3.2 Polarization analysis and filtering

Assume that the data file `data3c.su` is in the correct format to be processed with `supolar` and `supofilt` (Section 4.3.1). The shell script (`sh/ksh/bash`) printed below runs a polarization analysis of `data3c.su` with a window length of 0.1 s (see Section 2), and computes the direction cosines and the rectilinearity *RL* (Equation 11; defaults of `supolar`). The contrast factor for *RL* is set to $Q = 0.5$. Additionally, the incidence

angle Θ in degrees (Equation 5) and the flatness coefficient f_1 (Equation 16) are computed. The output files of `supolar` have the prefix `polar` (default) and the respective parameter flag as suffix, e.g. `polar.rl` for *RL* and `polar.theta` for the angle Θ .

The polarization filter uses *RL* as the weighting function (Equation 21) and raises the directivity function (Equation 22) to the power of $K = 2$. The default setup of `supofilt` reads the filter functions from the files `polar.rl` and `supolar.dir`, i.e. they do not need to be specified explicitly here.

```
#!/bin/sh
#-----
# Example shell script for SUPOLAR and SUPOFILT (N.M., April 2001)
#-----
# This script assumes that individual components can be identified by the
# trace header trid. The traces in the input file must be in the correct
# order, i.e. three adjacent traces belong to one three-component recording
# (vertical component first).

### User input (variables):
# Set the correlation window length wl to about one to two
# times your main signal period. Additional output files are
# polar.rl, polar.dir, polar.theta, and polar.fl for the
# computed polarization attributes.

wl=0.1          # correlation window length in seconds
rlq=0.5         # contrast factor of rectilinearity
infile=data3c.su # input three-component data file
wpow=1         # exponent of weighting function (here RL)
dpow=2         # exponent of directivity function
outfile=pofi3c.su # output file (polarization filtered data)
trid=12        # trid of component to be displayed after filtering

### Polarization analysis and screen display of results:

supolar <$infile wl=$wl rlq=$rlq verbose=1 angle=deg theta=1 fl=1

suximage <polar.rl legend=1 bclip=1 wclip=0 cmap=hsv2 windowtitle=rl \
  title="rectilinearity factor, q=$rlq" labell="time [s]" &

suximage <polar.fl legend=1 bclip=1 wclip=0 cmap=hsv2 windowtitle=f1 \
  title="flatness coefficient" labell="time [s]" &

suop <polar.theta op=abs |
  suximage legend=1 bclip=90 wclip=10 windowtitle=theta cmap=hsv0 \
  title="deviation from vertical in degrees" labell="time [s]" &

### Polarization filter and extraction of one component for display:

supofilt <$infile >$outfile wpow=$wpow dpow=$dpow verbose=1

suwind <$infile key=trid min=$trid max=$trid |
  sugain pbal=1 |
  suxwigb title="original data (comp=${trid})" perc=99 &

suwind <$outfile key=trid min=$trid max=$trid |
  sugain pbal=1 |
  suxwigb title="filter result (comp=${trid})" perc=99 &

exit 0
```

5 Additional programs

As already mentioned, *Seismic Unix (SU)* Release 35 or higher includes the program `suhrot` for simple horizontal rotation of three-component data. A rotation into the direction of polarization can be split into a horizontal rotation and a rotation by the (*P*-wave) incidence angle. Thus, although a bit complicated, such a rotation may be achieved with two runs of `suhrot`.

The alternative polarization analysis and filtering method described by de Franco and Musacchio (2001) is implemented in the *SU* program `sueipofi`. Also `sueipofi` interprets three adjacent traces as one three-component seismogram, i.e. data prepared as outlined in Section 4.3.1 can be directly processed with this program. Enter `sueipofi` or `sudoc sueipofi` for more information.

Kennett (2000) suggests semblance or phase-weighted stacking of three-component seismograms. For phase-weighted stacking, *SU* provides the program `supws` (type `sudoc supws` for details), and `sustack` may be used for an ordinary stacking (summation).

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